

POSSIBILITIES FOR IMPROVING THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH TRANSSPHINCTERIC FISTULAS OF THE RECTUM

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Relevance. A variety of studies and meta-analyses indicate that there is no single standard that fully guarantees the successful treatment of complex rectal fistulas, especially in transsphincteric forms [2, 3, 5, 7]. Traditional surgeries, although usually leading to recovery in most patients, are often accompanied by traumatic effects on the anal sphincter, which stimulates the search for new methods of intervention [1, 4, 6].

Purpose of the study is to improve the results of treatment of patients with transsphincteric fistulas of the rectum by improving the technical aspects of excision of the fistulous passage.

Materials and methods of research. The study is based on the data of examination and treatment of patients with rectal fistula operated in the proctology department of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University in the period from 2018 to 2023. 105 cases were selected for the prospective dynamic active study. Among them were patients with transsphincteric fistulas of the rectum. All patients were operated on routinely and, depending on the chosen treatment tactics, divided into two groups. The first group, the Control group, included 56 (53.3%) patients who had their fistulas excised using traditional methods. The second group, the main group, included 49 (46.7%) patients in whom fistula dissection was performed using modified instruments. Patients in the main group with transsphincteric fistulae underwent LIFT (Ligation of Intersphincteric Fistula Tract, i.e., ligation of the fistula tract in the intersphincteric space) with the elimination of the internal opening of the fistula at its base after turning it inside out into the rectal lumen. For this purpose, a modified button probe with an olive or a flexible cylindrical guide with an olive was used in case of a tortuous fistulous passage. In the presence of purulent accumulations in the pararectal tissue, in addition to excision of the fistula, we performed dissection, scraping of the walls of the

purulent cavity, washing with antiseptics and drainage of the residual cavity. The average age of the patients in this group was 45.3 ± 7.1 years.

Technical aspects. The operation was performed under spinal, epidural or combined anesthesia. The patient was placed on the operating table on his back with his legs bent at the knee and hip joints on special supports. The lumen of the rectum and the surgical field were treated with an alcoholic iodine solution. After standard diagnostic procedures, such as staining the fistula passage with a methylene blue solution and examining the fistula passage with a button probe, the exact location of the internal fistula opening was determined. An important stage of the operation was to carry a button probe through the entire fistula passage, since the probe served as a guide for the correct location of the fistula and to prevent damage to the wall of the fistula passage during its mobilization in the intersphincter space. A flexible cylindrical conductor developed by us was used for patients with branched and sinuous fistula passages. The intersphincter sulcus was palpated in the projection of the internal fistula. A semilunar incision 1.5-2.0 cm long was made along the furrow.

A part of the fistula was carefully isolated in the intersphincter space, avoiding damage to the muscle fibers of the anal pulp. Then, with the help of a dissector, the ligature was brought under the fistula. The inserted conductor was pulled through the external fistula opening to the intersphincter space, and after ligation of the distal part at the level of the recess of the rod, the fistula passage was tied with a ligature. When the probe was pulled back, the olive fixed the mucous membrane of the fistula and pulled it into the lumen of the rectum, thus the proximal part of the fistula turned into the lumen of the rectum. The fistula was cut off at the very base after stitching and bandaging. It should be noted that the operation was performed without traumatization of the anal sphincter. After ligation and crossing of the fistula, a sample was performed with the introduction of a methylene blue solution through the external fistula opening. When the stroke was sealed, the dye did not penetrate into the wound, but completely flowed back through the external fistula opening. If the tightness was insufficient, the dye began to flow into the wound. However, this was not a criterion for the unreliability of the operation, since it is more important to ensure the tightness of the fistula stump in the area of the internal sphincter. In case the dye got into the wound, the stumps of the fistula were additionally immersed in separate sutures with vicryl 2-0 with the capture of the external sphincter. The walls of the peripheral part of the fistula, in the absence of congestion in the pararectal tissues, were scraped through the external fistula

opening using a Volkmann spoon. With a deep location of the fistula passage and an extended wound, a latex drainage was installed in the intersphincter space between the sutures. If there was no inflammatory process and abundant discharge, the drainage was removed after 3-5 days. In transsphincter fistulas with purulent cavities in the pararectal cellular spaces, the fistula passage was also crossed in the intersphincter space (LIFT).

The results of the study. In patients who underwent LIFT surgery using modified conductors and without disruption of the muscle fibers of the anal pulp, there was a significant decrease in the level of pain in the postoperative period and after acts of defecation. This reduction in pain reduces the need for narcotic analgesics and significantly improves the quality of life of patients. During the first two days after surgery, patients in the main group had daily aseptic bandages changed in the perianal area, after which daily dressings were no longer required. This made it possible to reduce the burden on medical personnel and reduce the consumption of dressing material. In the Control group, daily bandages were performed with periodic tightening of the ligature every 4-5 days before its removal. The low invasiveness of surgery using modified conductors without damaging the muscle fibers of the anal sphincter had a significant impact on the length of stay of patients in the hospital. On average, patients of the main group spent 10.1 ± 2.2 days in the hospital (the preoperative period was 3.2 ± 3.2 days, the postoperative period was 7 ± 1.9 days). The duration of inpatient treatment was determined by the need for a comprehensive examination, including fistulography, ultrasound examination of the rectum and pararectal tissue, as well as magnetic resonance imaging. After the introduction of a new algorithm for examination and treatment, 15 patients operated on in 2021 managed to reduce the length of hospital stay to 7.9 ± 1.1 bed days. In the Control group, the average length of hospital stay was 17.4 ± 3.1 days (preoperative period - 5.3 ± 3.1 days, postoperative - 11.4 ± 2.2 days).

Conclusions: The developed innovations in the technical aspects of surgical treatment of patients with transsphincter rectal fistulas led to an improvement in the standards of medical care, reducing the frequency of immediate postoperative complications from 8.9% to 2.0%. The use of a modified button probe and a flexible cylindrical conductor with an olive tree in the surgical treatment of transsphincter rectal fistulas not only simplifies the process of technical implementation, but also prevents damage to the muscle fibers of the anal pulp.

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